

Industrial Manufacturing Strategies

For distributed control and resilient, rapidly responsive and reconfigurable supply chains.

CPPS for flexible & modular assembly of PCBs

Specialized mould manufacturing for the automotive sector

Twitter: @Modul4r_project
LinkedIn: Modul4r Project
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Tools manufacturing for the aerospace

Industrial Metaverse Simulations | Digital Twins

Resilience against changes in customer and societal demands and disruptions in the supply chain.

Modular Technologies for flexible manufacturing operations.

Simulation and interfaces to the Industrial Metaverse.

Human centred technologies and upskilling.